

The Role of E-Trust in Mediating the Impact of Website Quality and Google Ads on Repurchase Interest

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ABSTRACT: The primary objective of this study is to analyze the impact of website quality and Google Ads on repurchase interest in Bukalapak, with e-trust serving as a mediating variable. The sample consists of 105 Bukalapak users aged 17 and above who have made purchase transactions. The findings reveal that website quality does not significantly influence e-trust or repurchase interest, whereas Google Ads positively affect both e-trust and repurchase interest. Additionally, e-trust mediates the relationship between website qualities, Google Ads, and repurchase interest. This study offers managerial insights for online shopping platforms to enhance consumer retention strategies.

KEYWORDS Website quality, Google Ads, e-trust, repurchase interest, Bukalapak

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancement of the Internet has positively impacted the economic sector, particularly with the rise of e-commerce in Indonesia. According to research conducted by WeAreSocial in 2020, 90% of Internet users in the country visit online shopping websites (Detiknet, 2020). The ease of accessing product information drives this trend. Online buyers often make purchase decisions based on the seller's website, including its design and the quality of information presented (Daroch et al., 2021; Amsl et al., 2023). Websites serve as the primary platform for interactions between customers and companies, providing essential details about products and offers (Fernández-Uclés et al., 2020). These findings highlight the significant role of website quality in e-commerce, emphasizing its influence on user experience, ease of use, and trust (Ashiq & Hussain, 2024; Saoula et al., 2023).

In this context, raising awareness about online shopping security measures is essential for building e-trust (Zaheer et al., 2024). A key aspect of service delivery is website creation, where factors such as web load performance play a crucial role (Stringam & Gerdes, 2019). While existing research often emphasizes service quality and product information (Amsl et al., 2023), websites must also provide a user-friendly interface and functionality to help consumers easily access information (Phonthanakitithaworn et al., 2021). However, current studies on website quality remain limited in scope, leaving gaps in comprehensively evaluating website attributes. Effective website quality should encompass usability, information quality, and service interaction, particularly focusing on mobile application features designed to enhance electronic trust and purchase intentions during crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Zaheer et al., 2024).

Although the online market is growing rapidly, building consumer trust in e-commerce platforms remains a critical challenge (Ashiq & Hussain, 2024). Service quality, website quality, and reputation, mediated by trust, significantly influence purchase interest (Qalati et al., 2021). Previous findings have provided mixed results regarding the impact of website quality on e-trust, prompting a focus on post-purchase behavior, particularly repurchase interest. Customer trust shapes consumer circumstances and commitments, which, in turn, define the relationship with repurchase interest (Shahbaz et al., 2020).

In this digital era, consumers increasingly seek knowledge and information online ((Thottoli & Al Harthi, 2022). Google serves as a dominant information platform, with many e-commerce users relying on it to compare product reviews (Soeharso, 2024). According to Statistics Indonesia (2021), 71.23% of e-commerce sellers in 2020 sold directly to consumers, emphasizing the importance of service quality and e-trust in enhancing satisfaction and fostering repurchase intent (Bingwa et al., 2024). While much research has focused on digital marketing via social media, limited attention has been given to other avenues, such as Google Ads. To address this gap, research is needed to examine the interplay between website quality and Google Ads with e-trust as a mediating variable. E-trust is a strong mediator, as supported by existing studies (Kalia et al., 2021). Building on a literature review,

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this study proposes a research model centered on e-trust and repurchase interest. It posits that website quality and Google Ads must align to meet service expectations and consumer needs. The objective is to explore how post-purchase consumer behavior and service quality impact e-trust and repurchase interest

2. REVIEW LITERATURE AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

A. Website Quality

A website serves as an online platform offering information and essential services to users, playing a crucial role for companies dealing in goods and services (Einsman & Phen, 2000; Liu et al., 2011). Website quality significantly influences the purchasing process, as issues such as confusing layouts, payment difficulties, poor navigation, and misrepresentation of products can hinder user experience (Roy et al., 2022; Amsl et al., 2023). In the current digital era, websites are indispensable tools for businesses aiming to establish a strong online presence. They combine informative, relational, and transactional functions to meet diverse consumer needs (Fernández-Uclés et al., 2020). Consequently, businesses need to prioritize website quality. Websites should provide a user-friendly environment with efficient functionality to facilitate quick and seamless customer searches (Phonthanukitithaworn et al., 2021). Despite their importance, there is still ambiguity regarding the indicators needed to measure website quality effectively. To address this, further quantitative research is required to clarify and identify the key dimensions of website service quality (Phonthanukitithaworn et al., 2021).

The relationship between website quality and repurchase interest has been substantiated by several previous studies. For instance, Saidani et al. (2019) found that website quality positively influences customer satisfaction and repurchase interest. Similarly, Maulana (2020) reported a significant positive effect of website quality on repurchase interest. These findings align with the earlier conclusions of Saidani et al. (2019), further emphasizing the positive relationship between website quality, customer satisfaction, and repurchase interest. Building on this body of research, we posit that website quality plays a crucial role in shaping repurchase interest. Based on this rationale, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Website quality has a positive effect on repurchase interest.

A high-quality website can significantly impact how effectively information about a product is delivered to consumers. Factors such as the speed of access, ease of searching for information, informative displays, perceived security, operational simplicity, and overall user comfort in navigating the website contribute to building consumer trust in the capabilities or competencies of an online store, such as Bukalapak. These aspects are pivotal in enhancing the platform's market position. The frequent and detailed provision of information increases the likelihood of users trusting a specific brand or product. This notion aligns with Maulana's (2019) research, which indicates that website quality has a significant positive effect on e-trust. Similarly, Qalati et al. (2021) demonstrated a strong relationship between web design, perceived service quality, and e-trust. Cheung and Lai (2022) further emphasized that trust in the quality of website interactions, particularly in service delivery, is both continuous and significant. Based on these findings, we propose the following hypothesis:

H2: Website quality has a positive effect on e-trust.

B. Google Ads

The shift of information media to the online realm has established the Internet as a crucial source of information, with Google being the most prominent platform (Schwab et al., 2023). When users type a keyword or phrase into Google's search bar, advertisements tailored to the query are displayed on the search results page (Sijabat, 2021). Google Ads enables advertisers to target users by specific keywords, time, and location, making ad placement highly strategic and personalized. The use of Google Ads allows businesses to distribute information in a precise, effective, consistent, and appealing manner through advertising campaigns. This marketing strategy aims to increase consumer repurchase interest by continuously providing relevant and persuasive information. By reinforcing consumer perceptions of previously used products, Google Ads can encourage repeat purchases. Based on these insights, we propose the following hypothesis:

H3: Google Ads positively influence repurchase interest.

When advertisements displayed on the Google search page provide relevant information and indirectly offer goods or services, they can positively influence consumer trust in a product or service. This aligns with research by Maulana (2020), which found that website quality significantly affects e-trust. Similarly, as Google serves as a primary source of information for services and products, the strategic dissemination of information through precise, effective, consistent, and engaging Google Ads campaigns can enhance consumer trust. These campaigns serve as a vital marketing strategy to build e-trust by maintaining the credibility and appeal of the advertised offerings. Based on this, we propose the following hypothesis:

H4: Google Ads have a positive impact on e-trust.

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C. E-trust

Trust is defined as a party's willingness to be vulnerable to the actions of another party, based on the expectation that the latter will perform actions deemed important by the former, regardless of the ability to monitor or control these actions (Mayer, Davis & Schoorman, 1995; (Ashiq & Hussain, 2024). E-trust extends this concept into the digital environment, encompassing trust across all online platforms, making it essential to focus on building trust specifically within the context of e-commerce websites. Online retailers can increase consumer trust by minimizing perceived purchase risks (Qalati et al., 2021). In online sales, trust is further defined as an online seller's ability to fulfill obligations and establish lasting business relationships (Taufiq-Hail et al., 2023). When consumers trust a brand or product, their interest in making repeat purchases grows. The relationship between e-trust and repurchase interest is supported by several studies. Harjadi (2019) found a significant positive influence of trust on repurchase interest. Similarly, Maulana (2020) revealed that trust acts as an intervening variable, enhancing the effect of website quality on repurchase interest. Furthermore, customer trust is recognized as a key determinant of purchasing behavior (Fernández-Uclés et al., 2020). Based on these findings, we propose the following hypothesis:

H5: E-trust has a positive effect on repurchase interest.

D. Repurchase interest

According to Kotler and Keller (2022), repurchase interest refers to the tendency of motivated individuals to invest their money to enjoy products they have used before. It reflects the success of a company in providing satisfaction to consumers through the products or services offered. Repurchase interest is seen as the behavior of customers who respond positively to what a company has provided, thereby developing an interest in making return visits or re-consuming products from that company (Astuti & Abdurahman, 2022). It is the process through which people request products or services from the same or similar companies, and this intent often stems from a previous purchase (Ali & Bhasin, 2019; Phan Tan & Le, 2023). In line with this, repurchase interest plays a crucial role in the success of e-commerce, as it indicates consumers' plans to buy the same or different products from the same company (Yuniarti et al., 2022). This highlights the importance of fostering positive customer experiences to drive sustained consumer interest and loyalty in e-commerce.

Research Framework

Based on the discussion above, a proposed research model is proposed, as illustrated below.

Figure 1. Proposed research model

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To test the proposed conceptual model, this study employs a quantitative research method with a causal approach. This method is used to examine the causal relationships between the predicted variables (Malhotra, 2007). The research focuses on the Bukalapak e-commerce platform, which has experienced a decline in market position. As of 2023, Bukalapak ranked fifth in Indonesia's e-commerce industry, a drop from its third-place position in 2020 (Katadata, 2024). The study's respondents are users of the Bukalapak platform in Indonesia who are 17 years or older. A total of 105 respondents, selected through purposive sampling, participated in the study. The purposive sampling technique ensures that the sample consists of individuals who have relevant experience with the platform. According to research by WeAreSocial, 90% of Internet users in Indonesia engage in online shopping (Detikinet, 2020), reinforcing the relevance of studying Bukalapak users as a representative group of e-commerce consumers in

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the country. This sampling method and respondent selection aim to provide a clear understanding of the factors influencing consumer behavior on the platform.

Table I. Sample characteristics

Respondents			Respondent	
Gender			Work	
Male	20	19%	Student	46 43.8%
Female	85	81%	Private employee	28 26.7%
Domicile			Housewives	9 8.6%
DKI Jakarta	5	4.8%	ASN/Civil Servant	5 4.8%
NTB	32	30.5%	Entrepreneurs	17 16.7%
Bali	13	12.4%	Income	
Riau	5	4.8%	> Rp. 1,000,000 - Rp. 3,000,000/month	31 29.5%
Bengkulu	1	1%	> Rp. 3,000,000 - Rp. 5,000,000/month	35 33.3%
West Java	19	18.1%	> Rp. 5,000,000 - Rp. 7,000,000/month	26 24.8%
East Java	8	7.6%	> Rp. 7,000,000 - Rp. 10,000,000/month	12 11.4%
West Sumatra	1	1%	> Rp. 10,000,000 - Rp. 13,000,000/month	1 1%
North Sumatra	6	5.7%	Quantity of visiting shopping sites	
East Kalimantan	3	2.9%	Bukalapak	
Central Java	3	2.9%	Once	33 31.4%
West Kalimantan	5	4.8%	Ever 2 to 4 times	41 39%
Southeast Sulawesi	1	1%	Frequent	31 29.5%
Banten	1	1%		
Central Kalimantan	1	1%		
Gorontalo	1	1%		

Data for this study were collected through structured questionnaires, following the methodology outlined by Creswell (2018) and Ashiq and Hussain (2024). The questionnaire consists of two sections. The first section gathers demographic information from participants, such as gender, age, education level, income, and family status. The second section contains Likert scale questions that relate to the specific variables and hypotheses being investigated in this study (Bryan, 2016; Ashiq & Hussain, 2024). These questions assess the participants' levels of agreement or disagreement with statements concerning website quality, Google Ads, e-Trust, and repurchase interest, using a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The questionnaires were distributed using an online survey tool, Google Forms. Online surveys offer several advantages, such as being cost-effective and time-efficient, making them an ideal method for collecting data from a large number of respondents (Sulhaini et al., 2022).

The measurement of website quality in this study was based on indicators of usability, information quality, and service interaction, as adapted from Furkonudin et al. (2016). To assess Google Ads, the study used indicators such as click-through rate, conversion rate, cost per conversion, quality score, and search impression rate, which were adapted from Chris (2019). E-trust was measured using the indicators of reliability, intentionality, and benevolence, drawing from the work of Tong and Subagio (2020) and Astuti and Abdurahman (2022). Repurchase interest was measured through indicators of transactional interest, referral interest, preferential interest, and exploratory interest, as defined by Hasan (2018). The data collected from the questionnaires were processed using SmartPLS version 0.4 for structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis. The questionnaire consisted of twenty-six question items. The survey link was distributed via social media platforms and mobile messaging apps, including Facebook and WhatsApp, with the assistance of colleagues in various regions of Indonesia, ensuring a broader reach to target respondents. Quantitative analysis was employed to increase the accuracy of the results by including a larger number of data points for a more comprehensive assessment of the constructs, as noted by Hays (2018) and Ashiq and Hussain (2024).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When testing variable components, their validity and reliability are tested using Cronbach's alpha method. Table II shows that Cronbach's alpha value is greater than or higher than the applied limit value of 0.70 (Hair, J., Black, W, Babin, B., & Anderson, 2018). The development of a scale that calculates the value of the loading factor of >70 is considered sufficient. Meanwhile, the

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value of Average variance extracted (AVE) in each construct shows a value greater or higher than the general boundary value (Hair, J., Black, W, Babin, B., & Anderson, 2018) which produces an indication of convergent validity and reliability. When running a discriminatory validity test, we compare the square root of the AVE of each construct to its degree of correlation with other constructs. The results obtained confirm the validity of discrimination for each sample group.

When testing the variable components, their validity and reliability were assessed using Cronbach's alpha method. As shown in Table II, Cronbach's alpha values were higher than the applied limit value of 0.70, indicating good internal consistency, as recommended by Hair et al. (2018). The scale development process calculated the loading factor values, and those greater than 0.70 were considered sufficient for establishing reliability. Additionally, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct was calculated, and the results showed values exceeding the general boundary value, which indicates both convergent validity and reliability (Hair et al., 2018). For the discriminant validity test, we compared the square root of the AVE for each construct with its correlation with other constructs. The results confirmed the presence of discriminant validity for each sample group, ensuring that the constructs were distinct and measured appropriately.

Table II. Measurement Results

	Standardized Loading Factor	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Website Quality		0.952	0.957	0.585
Usability				
The Bukalapak website is easy to learn and operate.	0.657			
The Bukalapak website facilitates user interaction and is easy to understand.	0.754			
The Bukalapak website is easy to navigate.	0.784			
The design of the Bukalapak website is attractive.	0.636			
The Bukalapak website is competitive with other websites in the industry.	0.708			
The Bukalapak website provides useful and positive information.	0.791			
Information Quality				
The Bukalapak website displays accurate information.	0.814			
The Bukalapak website presents reliable information.	0.829			
The Bukalapak website provides relevant information.	0.823			
The Bukalapak website displays information that is easy to understand.	0.828			
The Bukalapak website provides detailed information about products and services.	0.801			
Service Interaction				
The Bukalapak website guarantees the reputation of its products and services.	0.735			
The Bukalapak website ensures security in transactions.	0.723			
The Bukalapak website ensures the security of personal data.	0.821			
The Bukalapak website delivers goods as promised.	0.741			
The Bukalapak website has a dedicated customer service section.	0.757			
Google Ads		0.898	0.925	0.711

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Click Through Rate (CTR)

The quality of message delivery in Bukalapak ads served on Google Ads is effective and well-received 0.868

Quality Score (QS)

The content of Bukalapak ads on Google Ads is highly relevant to you. 0.867

Conversation Rate (CR)

Bukalapak ad content on Google Ads encourages consumers to make a purchase. 0.797

Cost Per Conversation

Delivering ads that generate minimal costs 0.840

Search Impression Rate (SIR)

Bukalapak ad content frequently appears on Google landing pages. 0.843

Repurchase Interest 0.919 0.940 0.758

Transactional interest 0.908

Plan to repurchase products from Bukalapak within a certain period in the future.

Intend to make a purchase on Bukalapak in the next few months. 0.921

Referral Interest

Recommend products to others

0.903

Exploratory interest

Search for information about previously purchased products 0.826

Preferential interest

Choose products that have been purchased as the first choice 0.786

E-trust 0.886 0.929 0.814

Reliability

Bukalapak is an online buying and selling platform that can meet consumer needs 0.909

Intentiability

Bukalapak is a trusted buying and selling platform so that consumers feel guaranteed 0.905

Benevolence

Bukalapak is a trusted platform by providing the best service for consumers 0.892

In conducting tests on the validity of discrimination, the square root of the AVE of each construct is compared based on correlation with other constructs (Formell & Larcker, 1981). In Table III, the AVE is greater than the quadratic correlation, which confirms the validity of discrimination.

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Table III. Discriminant Validity

Variable	E-Trust	Google Ads	Website Quality	Repurchase Interest
E-Trust	0.902			
Google Ads	0.601	0.843		
Website Quality	0.508	0.638	0.765	
Repurchase Interest	0.730	0.718	0.465	0.870

In the data above, the bold print shows the root of the AVE Root for each construct

Table IV. Hypothesis Test Result

Variable	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Value	Conclusion
Total direct effect				
H1: Website quality has a positive effect on repurchase interest.	-0.090	1.019	0.308	Rejected
H2: Website quality has a positive effect on e-trust.	0.210	1.625	0.104	Rejected
H3: Google Ads positively influence repurchase interest.	0.483	5.643	0.000	Accepted
H4: Google Ads have a positive impact on e-trust.	0.467	3.772	0.000	Accepted
H5: E-trust has a positive effect on repurchase interest.	0.485	5.749	0.000	Accepted
Total indirect effects				
H6. There is an effect of website quality through e-trust on repurchase interest	0.102	1.506	0.132	Rejected
H7. There is an influence of google ads through e-trust on repurchase interest	0.227	3.133	0.002	Accepted

The results of the study, as presented in Table IV, indicate that only the hypothesis regarding website quality was not supported. Specifically, the findings revealed that website quality did not have a significant effect on e-trust or repurchase interest on the Bukalapak platform. In contrast, other variables such as Google Ads were found to have a positive effect on both e-trust and repurchase interest. Furthermore, e-trust was identified as a mediator between website quality and repurchase interest, allowing the hypothesis involving e-trust to be accepted. The study demonstrated that an increase in Google Ads by one unit resulted in a corresponding increase in e-trust by 0.467 units and repurchase interest by 0.483 units. Notably, e-trust had the greatest impact within the research model, where a one-unit increase in e-trust resulted in a marginal increase of 0.485 units in repurchase interest. This finding underscores the importance of Google Ads and e-trust in influencing repurchase interest, which aligns with previous research (Co & Ho, 2024) indicating that online trust is closely related to repurchase intent (Shahbaz et al., 2020).

Regarding the first hypothesis, the test results showed no positive effect of website quality on repurchase interest, and thus, this hypothesis was rejected. Potential explanations for this could include differences in the market context, user characteristics, and the specific quality dimensions of the Bukalapak website compared to previous studies. This is consistent with Wistedt (2024), who suggested that factors like usability, ease of use, and website reliability may not significantly impact purchase intent in certain contexts.

In contrast, the second hypothesis, which proposed that website quality positively impacts e-trust, was rejected, as the results showed a negative outcome. This finding contradicts previous studies (Bingwa et al., 2024; Qalati et al., 2021; Zaheer et al., 2024). The discrepancy might be due to differences in platform context, consumer behavior, or the unique characteristics of

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the Indonesian market, which may play a more significant role in influencing e-trust in Bukalapak.

The third hypothesis test confirmed that Google Ads has a positive effect on repurchase interest, which was accepted. This highlights the significance of leveraging digital marketing, especially through Google Ads, to enhance consumer repurchase intentions. By optimizing its marketing strategies and using analytics data from Google Ads, Bukalapak can better target its audience and strengthen customer relationships, ultimately improving the overall shopping experience.

The fourth hypothesis was supported, indicating that Google Ads promotion intensity positively influences e-trust. The more frequent and relevant Bukalapak's Google Ads promotions are, the greater the level of trust consumers place in the platform. By capitalizing on data-driven promotions, Bukalapak can boost its credibility, which is particularly crucial in the competitive e-commerce market. This finding underscores the role of digital marketing in fostering long-term consumer relationships, as highlighted by Schwab et al. (2023), those who emphasize the importance of credibility and effective branding in maintaining a strong digital presence.

Finally, the fifth hypothesis, which posits that e-trust significantly influences repurchase interest, was supported. The results show that as consumers' trust in the Bukalapak platform increases, so does their buying interest. This aligns with research (Duong et al., 2024; Ko & Ho, 2024), which stresses that e-trust is a key factor in building consumer loyalty and fostering repurchase interest (Zeqiri et al., 2023). To maintain and enhance repurchase interest, Bukalapak should focus on improving e-trust by ensuring transparency, data protection, and responsive service. These efforts will contribute to a positive, consistent shopping experience, ultimately sustaining consumer interest in repeat purchases.

5. CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyze the impact of website quality and Google Ads on repurchase interest through e-trust. The findings revealed that Google Ads had a positive and significant effect on both e-trust and repurchase interest. Additionally, e-trust acted as a mediator, positively influencing repurchase interest. In contrast, website quality did not have a significant impact on e-trust or repurchase interest. Consumers on the Bukalapak platform perceive the quality of the website as having little effect on their ability to find product information during the online purchasing process. This suggests that while website quality is important, it may not play as pivotal a role as Google Ads and e-trust in driving repurchase interest in the Bukalapak platform.

6. THEORETICAL AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATION

A. Theoretical implications

These findings have several theoretical implications. First, the study affirms the relevance of Google Ads as an effective digital marketing tool for building positive relationships with consumers. The results support the theory that relevant, attractive, and consistent advertising can enhance consumer interest in repeat transactions while fostering e-trust on online platforms. Second, the insignificance of website quality in influencing repurchase interest and e-trust highlights that, in certain contexts, this variable may not be the primary determinant of user experience. This suggests that the user experience on digital platforms is shaped not only by technical elements such as navigation and design but also by external factors like marketing strategies, particularly those involving Google Ads. Third, the study emphasizes the significant role of e-trust in influencing repurchase interest. This adds to the theoretical understanding of e-trust as a critical mediator in the relationship between marketing strategies and consumer behavior.

B. Managerial implications

Based on the findings of this study, several contributions to management practices can be proposed. First, consumers typically seek information about a product or brand before making a purchase, and Google remains the primary tool for product searches. Therefore, online shopping platforms must tailor their advertising strategies to align with their target market. Second, this study underscores the importance of website performance and quality as a service and communication platform. These elements significantly influence consumer experience, which in turn affects the level of online trust consumers have in the platform. Third, building online trust with consumers is a challenging and ongoing effort, requiring consistent interaction, information sharing, and product offerings without face-to-face engagement. Once online trust is established, it becomes a strong driver of repurchase interest. Ultimately, the key to success in online business is fostering repeat purchases through the development of consumer trust.

7. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study has several limitations. It focuses solely on investigating the consumer experience during the purchase process, particularly concerning Google Ads advertising and the website service experience. Future studies should explore broader aspects

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of consumer experience, extending beyond just advertising and website services to encompass other factors influencing purchase decisions. Additionally, further research is needed to identify key factors that shape consumer behavior in the Indonesian e-commerce context and to deepen the understanding of the relationship between website quality and e-trust. Since this research is confined to one e-commerce platform, Bukalapak, future studies should expand the scope to include other e-commerce platforms to enhance the generalizability and applicability of the findings.

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